

SEMANTIC-FUNCTIONAL FIELDS OF SUBORDINATING CONJUNCTIONS ACCORDING TO METADESIGNATE FEATURES

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Annotation: The concept of auxiliary words should reflect their development, dynamics, and changes. For this purpose, the characteristics of auxiliary words must be understood as a unity and struggle of opposites. Conjunctional means are used in forming internal relations within sentences and texts. Since the simplest forms of these relations include combination, connection, interaction, and subordination, such auxiliary elements are called conjunctional means.

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In traditional linguistics, many elements classified as subordinating conjunctions no longer perform this function today, as their roles have been taken over by other auxiliary means. From this perspective, studying subordinating conjunctions and revealing their essence is considered one of the pressing issues. Determining the semantic-functional fields of subordinating conjunctions according to their metadesignate features significantly helps to clarify these problems.

We define the following semantic-functional fields of subordinating conjunctional means based on their metadesignate (conceptual) features:

1. Based on conditional relations.
2. Based on temporal relations.
3. Based on locative relations.
4. Based on coalition relations.
5. Based on comparative relations.
6. Based on final relations.

The conditional relation represents the largest and core semantic-functional field of subordinating conjunctional means. In this field, the nucleus is formed by the conditional seme, while the periphery consists of semes derived from this core conditional meaning. The conditional seme serves as a general seme for the field, whereas causal, purposive, concessive, and resultative semes function as specific sub-semes. This field can be illustrated through the following diagram:

Figure 1. Semantic-functional field of subordinating conjunctional means based on conditional relations

These semes also follow a certain regularity in their peripheral arrangement. For example, since the resultative seme indicates an action occurring after the condition, it is located at the outer boundary following the nucleus, whereas the purposive seme is positioned before the nucleus. If we observe the dynamics of this field in a clockwise direction, first comes the purposive seme, then the causal seme, followed by the resultative seme, and finally the concessive (non-obstruction) seme.

In the conditional semantic-functional field, the nucleus is formed by the conditional seme, as every type of relation, in a broad sense, contains a notion of condition. In some relations, the conditional meaning becomes primary, while in others it remains secondary.

For example: “*Even though the weather was very hot, Yo’lchi was forced to harness the carriage*” (O). In this example, the fact that the weather was hot indicates that it did not prevent Yo’lchi from harnessing the carriage; at the same time, it also implies a conditional meaning that if the weather is hot, harnessing the carriage is unnecessary.

It is clear that this semantic-functional field represents a macrofield, which is further divided into microfields within itself. For instance, let us consider the semantic-functional microfield of the conditional paradigm. This field can be illustrated through the following diagram:

Figura 2. Semantic-functional microfield of the conditional paradigm of subordinating conjunctive means

In this microfield, the nucleus is formed by the explicit conditional seme (-sa), while the remaining semes represent peripheral phenomena. However, their relation to the nucleus is not uniform.

For example, semes expressing regret and pity (represented by the -da edi form) as well as semes indicating unrealized or impossible events (expressed by the -mas ekan form) are positioned on the left, i.e., the negative side of the field, and convey a negative semantic shade.

On the other hand, semes expressing certainty (-ki form) and desire (-mi form) are located on the right, i.e., the positive side of the nucleus, and convey a positive semantic shade.

The seme of a possible event (expressed by the -ar ekan form) is relatively neutral compared to the others. However, since it indicates a higher likelihood of occurrence than non-occurrence, it is still placed on the positive side of the field.

Figura 3. Semantic-functional microfield of the concessive (non-obstruction) paradigm

This field is centered on the implicit conditional form **-sa ham**, which constitutes the nucleus of the microfield. The remaining semes are positioned on the left side of the nucleus, i.e., on the negative side.

This is because they express attitudes toward unrealized or non-actualized events. For example: *“Although the situation in the mine is severe, for some reason there are not many patients in the hospital” (As.M.)*. In this sentence, there is an implicit expectation that there should be many patients in the hospital due to the severe condition in the mine; however, as noted above, the statement reflects a situation in which the expected outcome has not occurred.

Thus, each paradigm forms a semantic-functional field, and the peripheral phenomena within it are also organized around the nucleus according to a specific regular pattern.

Figura 4. Semantic-functional field of the temporal relations paradigm

In this field, the nucleus is formed by the temporal seme, while the remaining paradigmatic units are distributed around this temporal core within a specific peripheral structure.

Events expressed in **boundary** (*chegaraviy*) and **disjunctive** (*ayiruv*) relations are positioned at two opposite poles of the field, as they represent mutually contrasting directions of temporal development. In boundary relations, the event in the main clause occurs first, followed by the event in the subordinate clause. In contrast, in disjunctive relations, the event in the subordinate clause occurs first, followed by the event in the main clause.

In **continuative relations**, the development of events is closely interconnected; one action unfolds while another simultaneously takes place (EG(BG)EG). Therefore, this type of relation occupies a neutral position in the lower part of the field.

For example: *“While I was listening to Gulbahor’s song, those stormy days passed before my eyes” (E.V.)*. This sentence expresses a continuative temporal relation.

Thus, all types of relations within the temporal paradigm are systematically organized around the temporal nucleus according to their specific functional and semantic properties.

Figura 5. Semantic-functional field of the local (locative) paradigm of subordinating conjunctive means

In this field, the nucleus is formed by the general spatial (locative) seme, while the remaining specific meanings are considered peripheral phenomena around this nucleus.

The arrangement of these phenomena within the field also follows a certain regular pattern. If we observe the dynamics of the field in a clockwise direction, first the feature of spatial emergence appears; therefore, it is positioned in the upper part of the field. Next comes spatial movement or orientation, which is located on the right side of the nucleus. After that, another type of spatial movement or direction is realized, which is positioned on the left side of the nucleus.

For example: *“Where the people are, I would be there as well”* (Ya.). This example expresses the place of emergence of a spatial feature.

Thus, the locative paradigm represents a structured semantic-functional field in which all elements are systematically organized around the central spatial seme according to their functional-spatial relations.

Figura 6. Semantic-functional field of the coalition (coordination/associative) relations paradigm of subordinating conjunctive means

In this field, the nucleus is formed by the seme of relativity, as this type of relation expresses a general correlation that clarifies the abstract pronoun in the main clause.

The peripheral elements include the relations of person and specification. The personal relation is positioned before the nucleus, i.e., on its positive side, since the focus is placed on a human subject. For example: *“Whoever believes that something good will come out of the work is the real master.”*

The explanatory relation is located on the left side of the nucleus, i.e., after it, occupying a subsequent position. In this type of relation, an inanimate object, action, or another element becomes abstract and requires clarification. This relation is characterized by the presence of opposition within its semantic structure.

Thus, the paradigm represents a semantic-functional field in which relational meanings are systematically organized around the central seme of relativity, with peripheral meanings distributed according to their functional-semantic roles.

Figura 7. Semantic-functional field of the comparison (comparative) relations paradigm of subordinating conjunctive means

In this field, the nucleus is formed by the seme of comparison, while relations of gradation, analogy, and comparison are positioned in its periphery. These relations are located at an equal distance from the nucleus, since each of them contains a form of opposition (contrast).

For example: *“The more languages a person knows, the richer their inner world becomes” (PD).*

Thus, linguistic system phenomena also consist of a central field (nucleus) and adjacent zones (periphery). The semantic-functional fields of language phenomena can be defined both according to formal features and conceptual (notional) features.

In conclusion, studying language as a field helps to scientifically understand the dialectical relationship between the world, consciousness, and language. The theory of fields enables a holistic understanding of linguistic phenomena, the selection of the most necessary elements in communication, and ensures semantic interconnectedness among language units.

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